

Information and Communication Technology: Challenges & Business Opportunities

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Web Content Management System

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Abstract

Oftentimes, most websites start small and grow little by little as owners continue adding up content along the way. A website that started small and has become quite large through the years may present some serious problems to the web developer. Such problems may not exist during the early years of the website's existence. But as they grow, such problems slowly crop up until such a time that they can become unmanageable and may affect the whole website's usability.

The problem of effectively managing a website that was growing in size and complexity was the research focus. Determining efficient and sustainable processes to assure high quality online communications was the primary purpose of the research. The research makes a case to deploy enterprise web content management systems.

Keywords: Web, Content, Technology, Management.

Current State of the WCMP Art

A **web content management system** (WCMS) is a software system that provides website authoring, collaboration, and administration tools designed to allow users with little knowledge of web programming, languages, or markup language to create and manage website content with relative ease. A robust WCMS provides the foundation for collaboration, offering users the ability to manage documents and output for multiple author editing and participation.

A web content management system is software used for creating and managing website content. It is used to control a large, dynamic collection of web material such as documents and their associated images. A web content management system facilitates content creation, editing, workflow, and many essential web maintenance functions. Prior to this system all website updates were submitted to a single person that manually formatted the content. With the content management system in place any authorized employee could submit and maintain content. Once submitted, automated workflow routines routed content to the appropriate managers for review and approval.

The purpose of this research is to identify efficient and sustainable organizational processes to assure high quality online communications. Publishing accurate, timely, and error-free content is critical because the site is an important community resource with a rapidly growing user base and because it is a reflection of the fire district's commitment to customer service and quality.

To begin this research it is imperative to recognize who and why people visit the website and what features and capabilities are desired by those users. Once quantified and understood, processes and methods can be identified to assure that content is accurate and appropriate if page authoring and publication were decentralized.

Decentralization is accomplished primarily by separating content from technical formatting eliminating the need for special skills to publish to the website. This improves non-technical users' productivity and enables technical staff to focus on network and system level tasks. The concept of separating content from formatting is considered key to successfully addressing current limitations.

The research will also explore quality management challenges that might arise in a heuristic, flexible and self-perpetuating distributed content model and how appropriate oversight should be structured. This research paper used the descriptive research method to analyze, synthesize, and present the findings.

Key Applications of Web CMS :

CMS product that is one of the best Content management systems available on the web. The online content management software is allows management of several websites using a single CMS. Our other services in CMS domain include

- Website content management systems
- Custom CMS Software development & outsourcing
- Web content management systems
- Online CMS for ecommerce and medical CMS
- Workflow and Template management
- Coldfusion Content management system
- Enterprise Content management systems
- Portal CMS development
- .Net Content management system

Background and Significance

A **content management system (CMS)** is the **collection of procedures** used to manage work flow in a collaborative environment. These procedures can be manual or computer-based. The procedures are designed to do the following:

- Allow for a large number of people to contribute to and share stored data
- Control access to data, based on user roles (defining which information users or user groups can view, edit, publish, etc.)
- Aid in easy storage and retrieval of data
- Reduce repetitive duplicate input
- Improve the ease of report writing
- Improve communication between users

In a CMS, data can be defined as nearly anything: documents, movies, pictures, phone numbers, scientific data, and so forth. CMSs are frequently used for storing, controlling, revising, semantically enriching, and publishing documentation. Serving as a central repository, the CMS increases the version level of new updates to an already existing file. Version control is one of the primary advantages of a CMS.

The casual nature of this assignment results in the site commonly containing out-of-date or obsolete information such as details of an event that has already been held or a discontinued program or service remaining visible. It is also common for the site to contain broken or misdirected links, misspellings, improperly prepared images, and other errors that would be caught by editorial oversight.

Content for the site comes from a wide range of sources and includes board agendas and minutes, public training course calendars, job announcements, incident photos and videos among many others. Sending these items to a single employee working a shift schedule creates a bottleneck that frustrates those on both sides of the process.

HTML is an abbreviation for Hypertext Markup Language, the predominant language for web pages. It provides a means to describe the structure of text-based information in a document. All website pages are individually-coded static HTML files with essentially no relationship to each other. This makes syntax and design errors difficult and time consuming to repair and precludes any global changes to the look and feel of the site. Changes can only be made by someone familiar with a web language such as

HTML and even then changes are on an error prone page-by-page basis. Fixing and reposting these pages takes knowledge of other technical products such as a FTP client. FTP is an abbreviation for File Transfer Protocol. FTP is used to transfer data from one computer to another over the Internet and is a common method of publishing web pages. More sophisticated tools are available today to automate core navigation, design and publishing tasks that all but eliminate these technical impediments for content authors. The Web CMS based website hosts number of visitors each day. This number continues to grow as the expands the use of this popular online communication tool.

A centralized webmaster model is a hierarchy where a single individual with HTML expertise manages all aspects of a website. This role typically encompasses all planning, coding, production, and user interface responsibilities. To accomplish a successful transition from a centralized webmaster model to a distributed model requires a new way of doing business. Original content authors can no longer simply focus on the primary purpose of their writing. They must consider the repurposing of the material to the website as well as the original audience and presentation format. They must also embrace the additional task of publishing their material directly to the website. They will no longer be able to simply forward their work in its original form to the webmaster for formatting and posting.

Successfully decentralizing website publishing will require that employees across the organization learn new skills, take on roles in new workflow processes, and assume new and greater responsibilities.

A well developed agency website can play an important role in addressing these objectives though the use of multimedia lessons, instructional games and other online educational activities.

Content Management Problems and Open Source Solutions

The open source community has produced a number of useful, high quality content management systems which presents an opportunity to deliver tailored content management solutions without the high licensing or management fees associated with commercially-licensed or hosted software. However, the sheer number of open source CMS projects and the ineffectualness of traditional commercial software selection techniques can make the task of finding the right open source software an intimidating challenge. The strategy of using feature matrices is particularly ill-suited to open source software selection. A more practical approach is to match your needs to a

common business problem that others have solved using open source software and engage with the community to learn about their experiences in implementing the solution.

Open source content management software is most frequently used in small to medium sized web sites with very common requirements (such as corporate identity websites and departmental intranet sites or online magazines rather than large product websites with hundreds of thousands of pages) and as a foundation for building unique, highly-customized solutions (such as Amazon.com which uses open source components such as Perl, MySQL, and the Mason templating engine). Interestingly, the interconnectedness of the web and technologies such as portals, search, and RSS, can make having several small and medium sites more practical than trying to standardize on a single central platformⁱⁱⁱ. Large companies do not need to construct a monolithic intranet platform if smaller departmental sites can be integrated into a comprehensive intranet. Regardless of whether there is one system with multiple sub-sections or multiple sites, the same challenges of management and organization exist. While no commercial vendor has solved the problem of programmatically taming large volumes of poorly managed content in one repository, the technology that drives basic web sites and web-based content applications has become commoditized. Market leaders in the commercial space have tried to differentiate by adding features that clutter their products, making it hard for them to deliver a simple solution that meets a basic need. Open source creates an opportunity to target a common problem directly and save money that can be redirected toward training and creating better content. Open source can also enable more flexibility to manage the evolution of the application as requirements change.

Procedure

A content management system is the collection of procedures used to manage work flow in a collaborative environment.

A content management system is a computer application used to create, edit, manage, and publish content in a consistently organized fashion. CMSs are frequently used for storing, controlling, versioning, and publishing industry-specific documentation such as news articles, operators' manuals, technical manuals, sales guides, and marketing brochures. The content managed may include computer files, image media, audio files, video files, electronic documents, and Web content.

- * Allow for a large number of people to contribute to and share stored data

- * Control access to data, based on user characters

- * Easy storage and retrieval of data

- * Reduce repetitive duplicate input

- * The ease of report writing

- * Improve communication between users

List of Content Management Systems:

1. Joomla: Considered to be in the top three of any CMS list, by any CMS user. Joomla has been used to build many corporate and professional websites, such as the United Nations page.

Screen shot Joomla Admin for Web Content Management System.

DOTNET Sharepoint : Microsoft SharePoint is a web application that enables users within an organization to work together, collaborate, more efficiently through its vast number of features.

Screen shot of the Microsoft Sharepoint for Web CMS.

Although collaboration is at the heart of SharePoint, it includes many other important core features to help in the following business needs:

- Document Management
- Web Content Management
- Business Process Management (Workflows)
- Enterprise Search
- Business Intelligence (Dashboards, Reports)
- Electronic Forms (InfoPath)
- Social Networking

And that's just out-of-the-box features. Not only can all these features be customized to fit any organization but SharePoint can also serve as a platform to build solutions (custom applications) for any type of organization or need.

2. Drupal: One of the most popular and powerful content management systems available. Many believe Drupal is the best.
3. WordPress: While this CMS was originally made for blog publishing, it has quickly become a one of the most popular CMSs on the planet.

Recommendations

When a website has grown to the point where information cannot be consistently published in a timely and accurate manner, the implementation of a web content management system should be considered. A web content management system can provide an efficient and sustainable method to assure high quality online communication.

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